

Mitis

High-efficiency decentralised energy converters

Founded in 2012, Mitis specialises in the development of high-speed turbomachinery (c. 100,000 rpm) and system integration. Its aim is to contribute to decarbonization by deploying efficient, decentralized and clean systems combining heating, cooling and electricity generation.

With an annual turnover of €1 m (not including European subsidies allocated to R&D for its products), Mitis is able to develop systems from a blank page thanks to its modelling skills, its engineering capacity in high-precision mechanics and electronics, and its testing capacity (test rigs). The company develops its own products (combined heat and power microturbines) as well as products for third parties. For example, it is currently developing for ESA together with other Belgian partners a 120kW UPS (Uninterruptable Power Supply) using a hydrogen PEM fuel cell for deployment at the Kourou Space Launch site in French Guiana.

Mitis stands out in particular for its flameless combustion microturbine solution, a micro-CHP system that converts any fuel, preferably of renewable origin, into electricity and heat. The energy contained in the fuel is converted into thermal energy using its patented combustion technology, which burns the fuel in a low-pollution way thanks to very low NOx emissions (nitrogen monoxide, a greenhouse gas). What's more, this solution would emit less CO₂ for the same amount of energy used in comparison to large centralized power plants. This machine rotates very quickly on oil-free aerodynamic air bearings, which means that maintenance intervals are very long, thereby reducing the total operating cost of the machine. What's more, the machine emits very little noise and can handle all types of gaseous (natural gas, biogas, propane) and liquid fuels. An ideal product for heat-consuming applications that want to produce their own electricity at low cost (at the price of fuel oil): nursing homes, swimming pools, hotels, spas, residential buildings, etc. Another interesting application is biogas from agriculture or wastewater treatment.

Since inception, Mitis closed several rounds of financing. The latest private equity funding dated July 2022 amounted to €2.5m. Three new shareholders, including the SRIW W.I.N.G. fund (now Wallonie Entreprendre) and two families joined the original shareholders such as NOSHAQ. The team has been growing rapidly in the last 3 years, from 4 people in 2020 to 17 today. And that's not the only source of satisfaction for Mitis, one of two Walloon companies in 2020 to be awarded an 'Accelerator' project by the European Commission's European Innovation Council (EIC). Another source of pride: Mitis is the coordinator of a Horizon Europe R&D project: Fit4Micro. Launched in October 2022 for a period of 4 years, this project involves 9 European partners and runs a budget of €3.5m. Its aim is to develop a new generation of two-stage microturbines based on liquid biofuels.

By 2024, Mitis plans to have its first product on the market: the 10kWe micro-10. This will require the development of production facilities and a network of partners across Europe with access to local markets and installers. The company also has contacts for expanding into North American markets. A new round of financing should be launched at the end of 2023 to achieve this objective. True to its R&D focus, Mitis intends to continue developing its own machines, as well as machines for third parties in sectors complementary to its microturbine. Fuel cells are also on the agenda. This diversification bodes well for the future.

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